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Qualitative Study on Globalization and Learning of English as a Second Language at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The phenomenon of globalization has brought about profound transformations in the landscape of English language pedagogy, particularly in non-native English-speaking countries like Nigeria. This paper explores Language pedagogy, English in a global world, and the implications of globalization on the teaching and learning of English as a Second Language (ESL) in secondary school in Nigeria. By addressing these key areas, Nigeria can better equip its learners to navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by globalization while preserving its linguistic and cultural heritage. This paper sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the recommendations and strategies essential for enhancing ESL pedagogy in the era of globalization.

Keywords: Globalization, English Language, Students, teaching and learning

Introduction

Globalization's influence on education has become a topic of increasing importance and research. As economies, cultures, and societies intertwine on a global scale, the significance of mastering a universally recognized language like English becomes undeniable. Integrating language teaching with the principles of globalization aids learners in not only communicating effectively but also in comprehending diverse cultures and perspectives, thereby promoting intercultural competence. According to Mohammed (2020), in his article "English Language and Globalization," English has evolved into a global lingua franca, being the primary medium of international communication, business, and technology. The demand for English language skills is intricately linked to the demands of a globalized world. Therefore, teaching English should encompass not only linguistic competence but also cross-cultural understanding and adaptability, preparing students for a world where interconnections and interactions transcend geographical boundaries (Omachonu, Abuh, & Alhassan, 2017). In the Nigerian context, the impact of globalization on English as a Second Language education is notable due to the country's diverse linguistic landscape and its participation in global markets. The challenge lies in equipping learners with the skills necessary to navigate this global landscape effectively. Innovative methodologies, such as project-based learning that encourages collaboration and problem-solving, can engage students in authentic language use while fostering a global mindset (Bamidele, 2023, Amadi, 2019, & Mahboob, 2018).

Concept of Globalization and English as a second language

Globalization has had a profound impact on the English language, transforming it into a global lingua franca. As people and information flow more freely across borders, English has emerged as the dominant language of international communication (Owolabi, 2016). This phenomenon is driven by several factors. Firstly, the economic dominance of English-speaking countries like the United States and the United Kingdom has contributed to the widespread adoption of English in business and trade. Additionally, the internet and the rise of global media have made English the primary language of the digital age, as most online content, from websites to social media platforms, is predominantly in English. As a result, English

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proficiency has become a valuable skill in many parts of the world, leading to a surge in English language education and learners worldwide (Altan, 2017). The globalization of English has not been without controversy. Dash and Gandhi, (2022) argue that the dominance of English can lead to linguistic and cultural homogenization, eroding the diversity of languages and cultures around the world. This concern is valid, as the spread of English can sometimes overshadow the preservation and promotion of indigenous languages and traditions. However, proponents of English as a global lingua franca argue that it fosters greater international understanding and collaboration, breaking down communication barriers in an interconnected world. English facilitates the exchange of ideas, knowledge, and cultural expressions, enabling people from diverse backgrounds to engage in meaningful dialogue and collaboration on a global scale (Alfarhan, 2016). In conclusion, globalization and the English language are closely intertwined. English has become the de facto language of global business, diplomacy, science, and the internet, reflecting the interconnectedness of our modern world. While it offers opportunities for communication and cooperation, it also raises concerns about linguistic diversity and cultural preservation. Striking a balance between the advantages of a global lingua franca and the need to protect linguistic and cultural diversity is a complex challenge for societies in an increasingly globalized era.

Globalization and English as a Second Language at Secondary School level

Language pedagogy, the art and science of teaching languages, plays a crucial role in equipping individuals with the skills and proficiency needed to communicate effectively in a foreign or second language. Effective language pedagogy encompasses a multifaceted approach that considers various aspects of language learning, including linguistic, cultural, and cognitive dimensions (Verplaetse, & Migliacci, 2017). One fundamental aspect of language pedagogy is understanding the principles of second language acquisition. Educators draw upon theories such as behaviorism, cognitivism, and constructivism to develop teaching methods that align with how individuals naturally learn languages. For example, the communicative approach focuses on real-life language use and interaction, emphasizing the importance of meaningful context and communication in the learning process. This approach encourages students to actively engage in conversation, problem-solving, and authentic language tasks to develop their language skills. Another essential component of language pedagogy is the selection of appropriate teaching materials and technologies. Effective pedagogy integrates various resources, including textbooks, multimedia tools, language software, and online platforms, to engage students and enhance their learning experience (Hyder, 2021). In recent years, digital technologies and online language learning platforms have become increasingly prevalent, offering learners opportunities for self-paced study and real-time language practice with speakers from around the world. Language teachers must adapt to these evolving tools and incorporate them into their teaching strategies to cater to diverse learning styles and preferences (Moin, Patra, Mitra, & Dutta, 2019). Assessment and evaluation are integral aspects of language pedagogy, allowing teachers to gauge students' progress and adapt their teaching methods accordingly. Assessments can be formative, providing ongoing feedback, or summative, measuring overall language proficiency. Effective language pedagogy uses a variety of assessment tools, such as standardized tests, portfolios, oral presentations, and peer evaluations, to comprehensively evaluate students' language skills (Todorova, & Todorova, 2018). These assessments not only guide instructional decisions but also empower learners to set goals and monitor their language development, promoting a more personalized and effective learning experience.

English has undeniably achieved the status of a global language, serving as a common means of communication internationally. This designation as a global language is earned when a language assumes a unique role acknowledged across the world, transcending borders and cultures. English, in particular, has been embraced by nations globally, resulting in English speakers being present in virtually every corner of the globe. With over 350 million native English speakers and an additional 430 million individuals using English as their second language, it has become a genuinely global means of expression (Chapelle, 2018). In our interconnected world, the necessity for a universal language for effective communication is evident. This global language facilitates international dialogue across various domains, including politics, economics, education, and private business, ensuring that individuals worldwide can connect, understand, and engage with one another effortlessly (Omachonu, & Offorma). Below are the roles English plays in the global world. English is of paramount importance in education, particularly for those aspiring to study at renowned institutions in English-speaking countries such as Australia, the UK, and the US. Students are acutely aware that a strong command of the English language is a prerequisite for pursuing academic excellence in these nations. To gain admission to world-class universities in these countries, they must successfully navigate standardized English proficiency tests like TOEFL, IELTS, PTE, and more. Undoubtedly, these assessments pose a significant challenge to candidates. However, conquering these tests opens the door to fulfilling their educational dreams and

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gaining admission to prestigious colleges or universities. The significance of English in the realm of technology cannot be overstated, as it remains a fundamental language for global innovation and progress (Rao,2019).

In today's interconnected world, English plays a pivotal role across various domains. The technical lexicon largely relies on English terminology, making it essential for staying updated on the latest global developments and discoveries through English-language journals and research reports. The internet's rapid expansion has fostered international interactions, and English has become the primary medium for cross-cultural communication, enabling people from diverse nations to understand each other (Jenkins, 2015). Proficiency in English is particularly vital in education, science, and technology, where specialists often require a global language for effective collaboration. Aspiring students aiming to engage with the world of information technology recognize the paramount importance of achieving the highest level of English proficiency in pursuing their careers.

English is commonly referred to as the international language of business, a title that resonates strongly in the current global landscape. With international trade continually forging new connections among nations, the significance of English in the business realm cannot be overstated. Beyond facilitating travel, English empowers individuals to effectively communicate and project themselves on the global stage (Gottlieb & Nguyen, 2020). In the context of worldwide business interactions, English serves as the bridge for expressing ideas and engaging with the international business community. Proficiency in this global lingua franca is indispensable, as it ensures seamless communication and avoids potential hurdles arising from language barriers when dealing with diverse stakeholders worldwide. English, as the most widely spoken language globally, assumes a pivotal role in fostering cultural exchange and global connections. Its ubiquity enables English speakers to immerse themselves in the rich tapestry of diverse cultures through translated literature and international cinema, thus transcending geographical boundaries and broadening their horizons (Omachonu, Abuh, & Alhassan, 2017). Furthermore, this shared linguistic thread weaves a seamless fabric among English-speaking nations, facilitating effortless communication and fostering stronger connections between countries, bridging cultural gaps, and promoting global cooperation. In essence, English serves as a catalyst for cross-cultural understanding and interconnectivity, promoting a more prosperous, more interconnected world.

Learning English offers a distinct advantage in the job market, as many employers prioritize language skills, particularly proficiency in English, due to the widespread involvement of companies in international dealings. During interviews, hiring managers often assess candidates not only based on their academic qualifications but also on their ability to effectively communicate in English. Clear and articulate expression is highly valued, even alongside outstanding educational backgrounds. Given the abundant opportunities to work with international organizations in today's global job market, individuals are striving to acquire English language proficiency. Once job seekers attain both oral and written communication skills in English, they gain access to job prospects worldwide. This trend is not limited to English-speaking nations, as even individuals from non-English-speaking countries like China and Japan are increasingly learning English to enhance their employment prospects in the global business landscape (Rao,2019). English has become the universal language of business in the modern globalized world.

Travel and tourism, bridging national and international realms, predominantly rely on English as the universal language. It serves as the common linguistic thread connecting international travel departments, agencies, and companies. When visiting foreign nations, effective communication is essential for engaging with local populations, making a shared language a necessity. English, as the international lingua franca, fulfills this crucial role, enabling tourists to explore any destination worldwide (Todorova, & Todorova, 2018). Recognizing its significance, international travel agencies prioritize recruiting individuals with proficient English communication skills to facilitate seamless interactions with tourists from across the globe. English is pivotal in global entertainment, notably in the film, television, and music industries. Hollywood, based in the United States, serves as the epicenter of these industries, using English as their universal medium to reach a worldwide audience. This choice enables them to promote their content globally, offering relief to people facing the strains and stresses of modern life. English-language entertainment encompasses a wide range, including cartoons, movies, TV shows, comics, and educational programs like Discovery, National Geographic, Animal Planet, BBC, CNN, Star Movies, and AXN. These channels not only entertain but also educate, aiding children and adults in improving their language skills, vocabulary, and knowledge. In essence, English not only entertains and informs but also serves as a key language in various fields, reflecting its ever-increasing global importance (Mohammed, 2020). Learning English has become essential, transcending regional and national boundaries.

Implications for Teaching and Learning of English as a second language at secondary school level Education in Nigeria

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Teaching and learning the English language in schools comes with several implications that educators and students should consider. These implications can significantly impact the effectiveness of language education. Sucharitha, (2022) and Hodges, Moore, Lockce, Trust, and Bond, (2020) consider the following implications for the teaching and learning of the English language in secondary schools in Nigeria:

1. **Cultural Sensitivity and Awareness:** Teaching English in secondary schools involves not only language skills but also an understanding of the diverse cultures and backgrounds of English learners. Educators should be culturally sensitive and promote awareness to foster inclusivity and respect among students.
2. **Multimodal instruction:** Recognizing that students have different learning styles, teachers should employ various teaching methods, including visual aids, audio resources, interactive activities, and technology, to cater to diverse learning preferences.
3. **Language Proficiency Goals:** Secondary schools in Nigeria must set clear language proficiency goals for students. These goals can be aligned with international language proficiency standards like CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) to ensure consistency and measurable progress.
4. **Differentiated Instruction:** Recognize that students enter the classroom with varying levels of English proficiency. Differentiated instruction allows teachers to tailor their teaching to meet the individual needs of each student.
5. **Language Assessment and Feedback:** Regular assessment of language skills is crucial. Formative and summative assessments can help identify areas for improvement. Providing constructive feedback helps students understand their strengths and weaknesses.
6. **Integration of Language Skills:** English language teaching should focus on integrating all language skills – listening, speaking, reading, and writing. This holistic approach ensures that students can effectively communicate in real-life situations.
7. **Cultural Exchange Opportunities:** Encourage language learners to engage in cultural exchange programs, language immersion experiences, or interactions with native speakers to enhance language skills and cultural understanding.
8. **Use of Authentic Materials:** Incorporating authentic materials such as books, news articles, movies, and songs into the curriculum helps expose students to real-world language usage and enhances their language proficiency.
9. **Technology Integration:** Utilize educational technology tools and platforms to create interactive and engaging learning experiences. Online resources, language learning apps, and virtual classrooms can enhance language acquisition.
10. **Teacher Professional Development:** Teachers should undergo continuous professional development to stay updated with the latest teaching methodologies, language trends, and cultural nuances to provide high-quality language instruction.

Support for English Language Learners (ELLs)

Schools should provide additional support, such as English as a Second Language (ESL) programs or tutors, for ELLs to ensure they can successfully integrate into mainstream English-speaking classrooms.

1. **Assessment of Progress and Outcomes:** Regularly assess the effectiveness of English language programs to make data-driven improvements. Monitor students' progress and adapt teaching strategies accordingly.
2. **Parental Involvement:** Encourage parents to actively support their children's language learning journey by providing a conducive environment at home and participating in school-related activities.

Incorporating these implications into English language teaching and learning in schools can help create a more effective and enriching educational experience for students and better prepare them for communication in a globalized world.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the impact of globalization and English as a second language at the secondary school level in Nigeria is a multifaceted phenomenon that presents both challenges and opportunities. The increasing global interconnectedness has made English not only a crucial tool for communication and access to global resources but also a marker of educational and socioeconomic success. This necessitates a dynamic and contextually relevant approach to English language instruction, emphasizing not only language proficiency but also intercultural competence and critical thinking skills. While challenges such as linguistic imperialism and the digital divide must be addressed, the integration of technology and innovative teaching methodologies can bridge these gaps. Additionally, fostering a culture of inclusive and culturally sensitive language education is imperative to ensure equitable access and promote the diverse linguistic heritage of Nigeria. In navigating the complexities of globalization, educators and policymakers must continuously adapt and collaborate to empower English language learners to navigate the global landscape effectively while celebrating their unique linguistic identities.

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Recommendations

To address the challenges posed by globalization and its impact on English as a second language at the secondary school level in Nigeria, it is essential to consider a multifaceted approach that encompasses both policy-level changes and classroom-level strategies. Here are several recommendations for improving the teaching and learning of English as a Second Language (ESL) in Nigeria in the context of globalization:

1. **Curriculum Revision:** The Nigerian educational system should comprehensively review its English language curriculum. The curriculum should be updated to reflect the evolving demands of globalization, emphasizing language proficiency, intercultural competence, critical thinking, and digital literacy. This can help learners use English effectively in a globalized world.
2. **Professional Development for Teachers:** Continuous professional development programs should be established for ESL teachers. These programs should focus on modern teaching methods, incorporating technology, and promoting intercultural communication skills. Teachers need to adapt to the changing needs of learners in a globalized world.
3. **Incorporate Technology:** Utilize technology to facilitate language learning. The integration of multimedia resources, online platforms, and language learning apps can make English language learning more engaging and accessible to learners. This approach aligns with the digital demands of the globalized world.
4. **Cultural Awareness:** ESL teachers should promote cultural awareness and sensitivity in the classroom. Globalization has brought people from diverse backgrounds together, and understanding different cultures is crucial for effective communication. Encourage learners to explore various cultures through language learning.
5. **Assessment Reform:** Rethink the assessment methods used in ESL education. Move away from rote memorization and focus on assessing practical language skills, communication abilities, and critical thinking. This shift will better prepare learners for real-world communication scenarios.
6. **Promote Multilingualism:** While English is essential, promoting multilingualism is equally important. Nigeria is a linguistically diverse country, and encouraging the use of indigenous languages alongside English can foster a sense of identity and inclusivity while supporting effective language learning.
7. **Global Partnerships:** Establish partnerships with institutions, organizations, and educators from English-speaking countries. Collaborative projects, exchange programs, and access to native English speakers can provide learners with authentic language experiences.
8. **Policy Support:** Advocate for policies that prioritize the importance of English language proficiency in Nigeria's globalization efforts. Adequate funding, infrastructure development, and clear objectives are vital to the success of English language pedagogy.

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